

Students feedback on the forced transition to online classroom during Covid-19

Parichat Chuenwatanakul¹, Anintaya Khamkanya^{2*}

^{1,2} Department of Industrial Engineering, Thammasat University, Thailand

Email: cparicha@engr.tu.ac.th, kanintay@engr.tu.ac.th*

Abstract

Social distancing has become a new normal for a university in Thailand due to the Covid-19 pandemic since mid-March 2020. All traditional classes in a face-to-face style, therefore, were forced to be conducted online. This study presents the survey of students' reaction to online classrooms and the adaptability to the online classroom of both students and instructors from the department of industrial engineering, Thammasat University. Students' feedback was collected after the first week of online classroom. The result shows that, in the beginning, there were several problems reported from students, such as the confusion of different platforms used among all courses, sense of isolation, lack of equipment of students, and limited skills of using the online teaching platform of instructors. The most recommended online classroom platforms by students are Zoom for online meetings and Microsoft Teams for learning management systems. It seems that the most concern for students is lacking peer interaction and the learning atmosphere as provided in the traditional classroom. The results of this study were then used as decisive information for the improvement of students' experience of the online classrooms.

Keywords: Student perception, Online classroom, Covid-19

1 Introduction

During Covid-19 pandemic in Thailand, the government has ordered shut down on most public places, especially school and university. Some universities in Thailand, at that time, are in the middle of the second semester of 2019. The university has no choices but to move to the online classroom for all courses (Thammasat, 2020a). After the first week of the forced transition to online classrooms, there were complaints from students. At Thammasat University (TU), we consider student voices as decisive information. Thus, the department of industrial engineering was then decided to obtain feedback from students, to improve students' satisfaction for the online classroom.

It is well known that collecting feedback from students is mandatory in a university. Generally, students' feedback is obtained at the end of a semester. As Covid-19 caused the forced transition to online classrooms, it is important to obtain students' feedback as soon as possible. Questionnaire is a predominant method to obtain feedback (Huxham et al., 2008). Although questionnaire has pitfalls in validity and reliability on the questionnaire design (Penny 2003), it is still the most commonly used mechanism to obtain feedback by far (Brennan and Williams, 2004) in most colleges and universities (Kember et al., 2002).

The survey research design was selected for this study to investigate the perception of students regarding problems and opinions on the related topics of online classrooms. It is very likely that the pandemic would be longer than expected. The results will be used to develop action plans to help students on the online classroom. More importantly, the results from this study could also help improve the classroom management for the online classroom in a similarly context. In this paper, the research methodology is presented in Section 2. The results and conclusions are then summarized in Sections 3 and 4, respectively.

2 Methodology

In the second semester of the academic year 2019, there were 226 undergraduate students enrolled in the department of industrial engineering, at TU. All students were asked to participate in this study, to share their thoughts after the first week of being forced to online classrooms. At TU, the online classroom is an optional

teaching method. Generally, more than 90% of classrooms are taught using the traditional face-to-face style. Thus, the online classrooms are new to both students and instructors.

The purpose of this survey was threefold: (1) to identify student readiness on equipment used for online classrooms; (2) to assess student's perception on the platform used for online classrooms; and (3) to investigate the problems from the online classroom. The questionnaires including both closed and open-ended questions were used to collect data. There are three main sections of questionnaires. The closed questions are used to observe the perception of students. The data analytics was done in Microsoft Excel. The open-ended questions were analysed using exploratory content analysis (Auerbach & Silverstein, 2003). The survey was distributed online to students after the first week of online classrooms. The response rate is 80%, 172 out of 226 surveys was returned with completed answers.

The first section of questionnaire focused on the availability of equipment and internet speed that students used for online classrooms. For the second section, students were asked to evaluate their satisfaction on the experience of using different platforms for online classrooms. See the list of platforms in Section 3. Students can select one of these four answers for each platform, which are (i) I have never used this platform; (ii) I have used it, but I do not like it; (iii) It is okay to use this platform; and, (iv) I would recommend using this platform for all courses. The third section of the questionnaire was set to observe students' concerns. There are eight questions with three levels of urgency to be answered by students. The options of answer are (i) I have never had this problem; (ii) I have some problems on this, but it is fine (I have fixed it already); and, (iii) this is a serious problem, I need immediate help. The students' concerns were also collected using the open-ended question which asks students to share their opinion or concerns in a required field. It is also used to verify the answers from the closed questions. Finally, the overall satisfaction was evaluated on a scale of 1-Not satisfied to 10-Satisfied.

3 Results

3.1 Readiness of equipment for online classrooms

The readiness of equipment for online classrooms is crucial to the learning effectiveness and equality in learning. Due to the difference in financial backgrounds of students' families, this section of survey aims to quantify problems of lacking in equipment for learning online. Four types of electronics equipment were used in the questionnaire. These include a personal computer (PC) of either desktop PC or laptop, a smartphone, a tablet, and a PC in any public space. Based on the survey, students own at least one device that can access the online learning materials. It was found that 77% of students have a PC/Laptop, 67% have a smartphone, and 42% have a tablet. From Table1, we found that 32% of students use one device for online classroom, where 8% use a tablet, 9% use a smartphone, and 15% use a PC. Moreover, 68% of students own two or more devices for learning online. The combination of devices owned are varied. The results from this section reveal that all students have at least one device to access the online learning material. The popular combination of owning two devices are a PC and a smartphone.

Table 1. Devices used by students for learning online.

<i>Type of Devices</i>	<i>Tally</i>	<i>Percent</i>
1 device	55	32%
- Tablet	14	8%
- Smartphone	16	9%
- PC	25	15%
2 devices	64	37%
- PC and Smartphone	47	27%
- PC and Tablet	8	5%
- Tablet and Smartphone	9	5%
More than 2 devices	53	31%
- PC+Smartphone+Tablet	52	30%
- PC+Smartphone+Tablet+Public PC	1	1%
Total	172	

For the speed of internet connection, there are about 9% of students experiencing problems from using low speed internet to learn online. Students mentioned that low speed of the internet causes inequality when instructors use the fastest response as a criterion to give bonus or let students answer the question with grade. The speed of the internet is graphed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Speed of the internet used for online classrooms

3.2 Perception on online classrooms' platform

The main platform for online classroom at TU is Microsoft Teams (MS Teams). TU have prepared supporting materials and technicians for instructors and students on using MS Teams as a classroom platform (Thammasat, 2020b). However, it is not a requirement that all courses must use MS Teams. Thus, instructors may use another online classroom platform if preferred. For this reason, students have to use several platforms for online learning. In this survey, we focused on ten platforms that are available for TU students without additional cost. The list of platforms and the result from the survey are shown in Table 2 and Figure 2. The top three platforms that have low negative feedback from students are Zoom, MS Teams, and Facebook, respectively. The top three platforms recommended by students are Zoom, MS Teams, and YouTube. It seems that Zoom is preferred by students in this survey. Note that Zoom is an online meeting platform that does not have the learning management system (LMS) at this moment, therefore another LMS platform must be used simultaneously. For these reasons, Zoom is considered as the most preferable online meeting platform and MS Teams is the most preferable LMS platform.

Table 2. Results of students' perception on platform for online classroom

<i>Platforms for online classrooms</i>	<i>I have never used this platform</i>	<i>I have used it, but I do not like it</i>	<i>It is okay to use this platform</i>	<i>I would recommend using this platform</i>
Email	15%	39%	40%	6%
Facebook Live/Group	22%	19%	52%	8%
Google Classroom	10%	39%	46%	5%
Google Team/Hangouts	5%	77%	18%	0%
Line Group/ Line call	20%	43%	35%	2%
Microsoft Team	10%	19%	50%	20%
TU GenNext	3%	85%	11%	1%
TU Moodle	5%	33%	53%	9%
Youtube	5%	30%	46%	19%
Zoom	8%	14%	53%	26%

Figure 2. Summary of students' perception on the platforms for online classroom

3.3 Problems reported from students on online classrooms

This survey was launched after the first week of online classrooms. There were concerns from students reported to the department continuously during that time. The list of concerns was then used to create the list of problems. Moreover, this survey also provided an open-ended question for students to inform their thoughts. The results of a survey regarding problems from the first week of online classrooms are presented in Table 3 and Figure 3. In summary, there are two problems that 90% of students have experienced, which are P6 – Confusion of online learning platforms used among different and P8 – Feel lonely, need to interact with friends during class time. Besides, problems P6 and P8 are also the top two problems that students think should be fixed immediately.

According to section 3.1, the survey result suggests that all students can access the online contents using their own electronic devices and around 10% of students encountered the problem of low speed of the internet. The results from problems P1 - P5 also suggest similar results, that is, around 10% of students have the problem of lacking equipment or internet connection. Moreover, since some courses require software that can only be used in a PC, students were mentioned via the survey that they need to borrow a PC. The department was then helping those students in need promptly.

Table 2. Results of problems reported from students on online classrooms.

Type of Problems	No problem	Problem solved	Need help
P1 – Unable to join the online classroom	64%	31%	5%
P2 – Unable to get points due to using low speed of the internet	37%	52%	11%
P3 – Have only smartphone to watch lecture video	39%	49%	12%
P4 – Loss of internet connection during live lecture	40%	46%	14%
P5 – Cannot download lecture video due to large file size	58%	36%	6%
P6 – Confusion of online learning platform used among different courses	8%	52%	40%
P7 – Feel sleepy during online classroom	53%	36%	11%
P8 – Feel lonely, need to interact with friends during classes	9%	27%	63%
<i>Additional opinions from the open-ended question</i>			
A1- Complain about the multiple platform used in a different course	n/a	n/a	14% ^[1]
A2 - Worry about the changes in course outlines and examination method	n/a	n/a	14% ^[1]
A3 – Prefer to not answering questions during live lecture and suggest about providing recorded video of the live lecture	n/a	n/a	19% ^[1]

^[1] Calculated from 227 pieces of comments from 172 students

From the open-ended question that let students share their opinions or concerns freely, students restated that they have the problems regarding the confusion of different platforms used among all courses. It was also found that students were also concerned about their study plan since all activities will be done online. The technical issues of online classrooms were also reported. Lacking experience in using an online classroom

platform of instructors was also mentioned as a problem from students' view. These problems are due to the sudden transition of the classroom. Finally, the satisfaction of the first week online classroom evaluated by students is 6.13 from scale 1-10. It is definitely lower than the expectation from the faculty members. The information was then sent out to all instructors in the department for improvement purposes. The corrective actions were instantly launched to solve the problems.

Figure 3. Summary of problems reported from students on online classrooms

4 Conclusions

Online classrooms are more likely to become the new normal for education in all levels. The results in this paper presented feedback from students that were forced to learn online during the pandemic. It was found that there were problems that arose due to the forced transition. Technical-based problems such as lacking of equipment or internet connection seems to have little effects on students' experience during the transition. Besides, lacking of peer interaction and uninspired learning atmosphere seem to be more desiderate from students' point-of-view. The feedback from students after the end of the semester has not yet been reported. However, it is expected that the action plan implemented based on the feedback surveyed in this study would help students to excel their online classes effectively for the upcoming semester.

Acknowledgements

This publication is a partial outcome of project „Curriculum Development of Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE4.0)“ that has been funded with support from the European Commission (Project Number: 586137-EPP-1-2017-1-TH-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP).

5 References

- Auerbach, C. F. & Silverstein, L.B. (2003). *Qualitative data: An introduction to coding and analysis*. New York: New York University Press.
- Huxham, M., Laybourn, P., Cairncross, S., Gray, M., Brown, N., Goldfinch, J., & Earl, S. (2008). Collecting student feedback: a comparison of questionnaire and other methods. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 33(6), 675-686.
- Kember, D., Leung, D. Y., & Kwan, K. (2002). Does the use of student feedback questionnaires improve the overall quality of teaching?. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 27(5), 411-425.
- Penny, A. R. (2003). Changing the agenda for research into students' views about university teaching: Four shortcomings of SRT research. *Teaching in higher education*, 8(3), 399-411.
- Thammasat (2020a). Thammasat University Notification on Measures and Suggestions on the Prevention and Control of Coronavirus 19 (Covid-19) (No. 6). <https://tu.ac.th/uploads/news-tu/images/mar63/file/Thammasat-University-Notification-Commencement-6-EN.pdf>
- Thammasat (2020b). <https://tu.ac.th/onlinelearning>
- Williams, R., & Brennan, J. (2004). *Collecting and using student feedback Date: A guide to good practice*. York: LTSN.